

Interactive Online And Offline Games: Their Influence To The Mathematical Aptitude Of Secondary School Learners

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Abstract: Playing interactive games, both online and offline, might pose risks leading to poor academic achievement. This alarmed parents and school authorities especially that the difference between game engagement and addiction has not been fully understood. The present study determined the influence of interactive games on the mathematical aptitude of secondary school learners. It was conducted at Halapitan National High School, Division of Bukidnon, for the school year 2018-2019, with 208 respondents from Grade 10 and 11 learners. The study utilized descriptive-comparative research design, while employing researcher-made survey questionnaire and National Career Assessment Examination results as main data gathering tools. The appropriate statistical techniques like frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to treat the data. Results revealed that the mathematical aptitude of the respondents was at *Low Average*, showing that the learners showed little knowledge and understanding in the mathematical concepts tested. Moreover, the extent of exposure of the learners in the study is *Slightly Exposed* to the different levels of interactive games. Further, there is no significant difference in the mathematical aptitude of secondary school learners when grouped according to the levels of interactivity of games they play and their extent of exposure.

Index Terms: Online Games, Offline Games, Mathematical Aptitude, Descriptive- Comparative Study, Interactive Games

1 INTRODUCTION

Playing online and offline games revolutionized the concept of fun and leisure across cultures and age groups. Mobile phones and internet connectivity make it even easier to play video games anytime and almost anywhere. With this accessibility, prevalent engagement with interactive games, especially among school learners, has caught a lot of attention from both parents and educators. This phenomenon been thought of as detrimental to the academic achievement and aptitude of the playing school learners. At present, offline and online games were very engaging in terms of its interactivity. The enjoyment derived from playing interactive games attracted both school-aged children and adults, who do not only play for recreation, but also take gaming as a career or a business. Exciting advances in the game industry created jobs such as game designers, developers, and so-called professional players. Online game tournaments are now considered as emerging sports and industry. As such, there is a need for learners to maximize and enjoy the fast-changing technology to improve learning. Learners need to develop skills deemed important for the 21st century workplace. Over the years, the Partnership for 21st Skills (P21) outlined the "4Cs" which were considered to be the most important in the K-12 curriculum (NEA, 2014). These skills are critical thinking, communication, collaboration and creativity. The current world economy and industries necessitate not only the 3Rs (reading, writing, and arithmetic) to be learned in school, but also the 4Cs. Good education then requires learners to become critical thinkers, effective communicators by using different platforms and digital media, to work efficiently through collaboration with other team mates, and innovate creatively new products and services. These skills may be developed by playing interactive games according to the Federation of American Scientists (2005). However, individuals

differ on motivations in dealing with interactive games. Preferences in genres or game types and their interactivity, platforms used (mobile phones, laptops, personal computers in internet shops) and levels of engagement also vary. According to Weber et al. (2014), differences between genres or games were significant for customization, artificial intelligence, perceptual persuasiveness, controller responsiveness, and exploration. It is believed that these differences in interactive games may also induce different outcomes or influences among its players (Buckley & Anderson, 2006). Ideally, developing the digital skills of learners should likewise enhance academic performance but this is not the reality. Many experts say that playing video games might pose risks leading to poor academic achievement, health, obsessive playing and behavior issues (Griffiths, 2007; Choo et al., 2010). This alarmed parents and school authorities especially that the difference between game engagement and addiction has not been fully understood (Seok & DaCosta, 2014). The common notion is that high engagement or frequent playing is associated with addiction symptoms. On the contrary, not all research points out to negative effects in playing online and offline interactive games. A number of researches informed that these games could serve as a vital tool to enhance learning inside the classroom. The studies of Squire (2006), Ferguson (2010), Gee (2007), Oehlert (2010), and Diezmann and Watters (2000) among others claimed that playing online and offline games develops spatial abilities, particularly visualization, mental rotation and provides opportunities for students to improve their problem-solving skills, critical thinking skills, and even language. According to some authors, playing interactive games do not significantly influence the academic achievement and aptitude of learners. In Halapitan National High School, it is observed that many learners play interactive games on their mobile phones. The researcher has observed that even during class hours, a few learners sneaked out and others do not participate well during classes just to play; while a good number play right after classes or only during their vacant time. Some teachers are even skeptical about interactive games and its effects on learners since records of the Guidance Counselor Designate showed that a number of students-at-risk of dropping out (SARDOs) mentioned interactive games as the primary reason why they decided to skip or be absent from their classes. As a

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Mathematics teacher, the researcher noted that the irregular attendance of learners who were hooked with interactive games contributed to low performance in class. Also, low engagement in Mathematics lessons was also observed where most of the learners claimed that Mathematics is either too boring or too complicated. However, it was also noted that several honor learners, who are doing well in their Mathematics subjects, also claimed to have been playing Mobile Legends and DOTA 2. Meanwhile, the performance and achievement of learners in mathematics subjects were also noted to be below the standards set by the Department of Education. In the year 2015, the result of the National Career Assessment Examination (NCAE) for the Mathematical Ability Subtest was 32.13% mean percentage score (Benito, 2016). In terms of National Achievement Test results of fourth-year high school students and Grade 10 learners from 2009-2015, Region X learners got an average of 48.6% for Mathematics (Victorino, 2018). Declining turn-outs in national assessments and achievements tests as reported could be attributed to distractions such as engagement with online and offline games and the so-called television shows (Cruz, 2012). Learners, especially in urban areas where gaming was more rampant, were less-focused with their studies because of their engagement with these media. This point of view is also shared by parents, teachers, and some education stakeholders. With these, the present study determined the influence of playing online and offline games on the mathematical aptitude of the secondary school learners of Halapitan National High School during the school year 2018-2019. It is believed that there is a need to look into the interactive gaming engagement and the mathematical aptitude of the learners and the possible educational gains that can be derived from it. Not much research has been conducted on the influence of interactive games on the mathematical aptitude of the learners. Thus, the present study tried to fill in the research gap. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the mathematical aptitude of secondary school learners?
2. What is the extent of exposure to interactive games of the secondary school learners?
3. Is there a significant difference in the mathematical aptitude of secondary school students when grouped according to the level of interactive games they play and their extent of exposure to those games?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This part of the paper presents the methods and procedures used in the study to determine the influence of playing interactive games on the mathematical aptitude of secondary school students. The discussion includes the research locale, participants of the study, data gathering procedure, instrument, and statistical tools. In line with the descriptive-comparative research design, the data gathering was done using validated researcher-made questionnaire and was supplemented by informal interviews with teachers and learners who shared their views and opinions on the topic.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Halapitan National High School, Division of Bukidnon for the school year 2018-2019. Halapitan National High School caters learners from the 24 barangays of

San Fernando. There were at least 8 internet cafés and gaming shops surrounding the school vicinity, where learners have easy access. A number of learners' own smartphones that they use to play interactive games during their vacant time. Further, the strong Wi-Fi connection and signal allow learners to have a play without interruption. The engagement in interactive games of Halapitan National High School learners especially those who have poor attendance in school caught the attention of the GPTA and the Sangguniang Bayan of the Municipality of San Fernando. Thus, Municipal Ordinance # 008 s. 2016 was promulgated to curb and regulate the access of learners to internet shops during school hours and beyond the curfew in the municipality.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were Grade 10 and Grade 11 secondary school learners of Halapitan National High School. These learners came from the six sections in Grade 10 and seven sections in the Grade 11. The participants are aged between 15 to 20 years old. A random sample of 105 Grade 10 learners and 103 Grade 11 learners participated in the study, for a total of 208 learners. Most of the learners used their mobile phones to play interactive games. Combined together, learners with personal computers, laptops, netbooks, and mobile phones have access to interactive games at the comfort of their homes. However, those who played online and offline games with laptops and netbooks and some with their mobile phones could play just about anywhere, even in school. Several learners, mostly boys, claimed that they are playing interactive games by teams at the internet cafes nearby or even participate in online game tournaments.

Research Instruments

The research instruments used in this study were the Learner Certificate of Ratings of the National Career Assessment Examination and a validated survey questionnaire. NCAE Certificate of Ratings (CoR) were used by the researcher to collect the actual data on the mathematical aptitude of the learners. Raw scores on the Mathematical Ability Subtest were considered as the aptitude result. The mathematical ability test is a sub-test of the General Scholastic Aptitude test in the NCAE. It has 40 items to measure the abilities requiring quantitative abilities and computational skills, particularly on working with numbers, perceiving relationships between two (2) quantities, and solving arithmetic problems. The researcher-made survey questionnaire was used by the researcher to reveal the frequency of video game play and the interactive games played by the learners. It consists of 18 interactive games ranging from highly interactive to slightly interactive. Five games consist of both highly and moderately interactive games, while 8 games composed the slightly interactive games. In the development of the questionnaire, the researcher conducted a preliminary survey of the interactive games played by the learners. The 185 learners surveyed listed at least thirty online and offline games. The researcher also consulted internet café attendants and operators in Halapitan, San Fernando, Bukidnon on the online games played by their customers. Frequent players of online and offline games were also asked to list down the games that they were playing. Taking every gathered data into consideration, a majority of 18 games were considered in the draft questionnaire and were classified according to their interactivity levels with the help of some experts. These

experts were secondary school teachers assigned in the junior and senior high schools who played Mobile Legends heavily at present, and who grew up playing interactive games even until they are now teachers. A questionnaire try-out was conducted. Upon the approval of the school principal, 100 Grade 9 learners answered the questionnaire. To determine the reliability of the scale instrument, a reliability test was done. The reliability test result of the instrument was 0.813. This shows that the instrument was reliable, dependable and consistent to assess the interactive games played by the learners, in terms of the extent of exposure and interactivity levels.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the implementation of the study, the researcher first asked permission from the office of the College of Education Dean of Bukidnon State University for the conduct of the study. Upon the approval of the dean, a letter request addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd- Bukidnon for the conduct of the study was submitted. The approved letter request was then endorsed to the School Principal of Halapitan National High School. With the approval of the School Principal, a random sampling procedure was done to identify the learners who will answer the questionnaire. The researcher worked with the guidance counselor and class advisers on the gathering the mathematical aptitude of the learner in the NCAE results. Informed consent from the identified participants and parents' consent were secured prior to the conduct. The participation was voluntary in nature. The identified participants were free to withdraw from the study. Before the students were given the questionnaires, the researcher first explained the objectives of the study and then, proceeded with the discussion on how each item in the questionnaire is to be answered. After the questionnaires were retrieved, the researcher made informal interviews about interactive games and their mathematics performance in their classes.

Treatment of Data

The data gathered were treated using appropriate statistical techniques. They were tabulated and organized into tables. To answer problems number 1 and 2, frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to determine the mathematical aptitude and extent of exposure to interactive games of the learners. To answer problem number 3, two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to compare the mathematical aptitude of secondary school students when grouped according to levels of interactivity of games they are playing and their extent of exposure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Mathematical Aptitude of Secondary School Learners

The frequency distribution of the level of mathematical aptitude of high school learners is presented in Table 1. As revealed, the mean NCAE score of students in terms of mathematical aptitude is categorized as Low Average. Learners show little understanding and little knowledge in the field of Mathematics. Further, results presented using frequencies and percentages showed that a greater number of learners attained Low Average (47%) and Average (37%). The figures show that the majority of the learners' mathematical aptitude can be described as moving from little understanding

and little knowledge towards achieving sufficient understanding and sufficient knowledge in the field of Mathematics. Findings suggest that learner-participants have the potentials to learn Mathematics, provided that intervention was done on areas in Mathematics that need to be addressed. The interventions have to be immediate and tailor-fit to cater to the needs of learners for them to do well in Mathematics. Relative to that, the results denote that, at present, the majority of the Grade 10 and Grade 11 learners did not acquire the expected mathematical competencies on their grade level. Further, their mathematical aptitude results revealed that only a little knowledge and understanding of Mathematics have been established, specifically from Kindergarten to Grade 9. It indicates that learners may experience difficulties in learning new materials or lessons in Mathematics. The mathematical aptitude of secondary students manifests the knowledge they have acquired in the previous years; thus, it may somehow predict their success in learning Mathematics in the higher-grade levels.

Table 1. High School Learners' Mathematical Aptitude Results

Aptitude Level	Range of Scores	f	%
Excellent	760.74 – 797.36	2	1%
Very High	674.07 – 760.73	0	0%
Above Average	602.93 – 674.06	9	4%
Average	486.08 – 602.92	77	37%
Low Average	389.49 – 486.07	98	47%
Below Average	318.34 – 389.48	22	11%
Total		208	100%
	\bar{x}		484.01
	SD		75.71
	Qualitative Description		Low Average

The results are supported by the findings of an independent review conducted by Basic Education Sectoral Transformation (2018) as part of a grant from the Australian Government to the Department of Education. The findings of the study revealed that conceptual knowledge and skills declined as a learner progressed from Grade 7 to Grade 11. Accordingly, the observed decrease in the readiness of learners to the grade level can be attributed to the spiraling approach of the curriculum. This means that skills not covered in the previous years will likely hinder the acquisition of new skills in the current year. There is an indication that Grade 10 and Grade 11 learners had encountered difficulties as they moved up from junior high school to the senior high school. The results corroborated with the findings of Herrera and Dio (2016) that the readiness of incoming Grade 11 students in the Division of Sorsogon is just moderately ready with a 40% MPS after completing a 50-item test on the necessary competencies in taking up General Mathematics. Grade 10 learners were not able to master the competencies and skills necessary to understand the concepts to be learned in General Mathematics. With that, learners need to exert more effort in learning Mathematics. Otherwise, there will be a higher possibility of failure in more difficult Mathematics subjects. Most of the time, learners complain about not being able to

comprehend on assigned readings in Mathematics in preparation for the next day's lesson. They also encounter difficulties whenever word problems are posed for them to answer. Even if they were able to master the computational skills needed to solve a particular problem, they lack the confidence to solve word problems stated in English. With this, the opportunity to hone their problem-solving and critical thinking skills were sacrificed either by the teacher or by the learners themselves. As part of the solution in enriching the lessons in both Grade 10 and 11 subjects taught by the researcher, YouTube clips or videos were used as a part of the Modified Flipped Classroom Approach to teaching. In the videos selected, the medium of instruction used is Filipino. After assessing the engagement of the students, the researcher observed that students become more interested of learning the topics being presented since they claimed that the explanations were very clear. Hence, it can be gleaned that learners were more interested in learning Mathematics when the lessons are contextualized in the learners' language. This observation is supported by Tapang (2018), where he expounded that Mathematics and Science subjects should be taught using the vernacular or in the language where students are most comfortable with. He further stated that in the 2003 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) conducted by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement, it was revealed that countries that rank high (except Singapore) have basic instruction in the mother tongue, while countries who are English-speaking are among the lowest. The findings of this study somehow explain the rank of the Philippines in the 2017 Global Competitiveness Report. The mathematical aptitude of the learners in the study falls under the Low Average level. From this, Mathematics and Science Education in the country has to improve its quality to produce globally competent graduates in the K-12 curriculum. The unsound assessment classroom practices of teachers were considered as one of the reasons why the problem still exists. According to Lugtu (2018), the use of graded recitations and examinations may tend to reward learners who memorized the lessons. In return, there was a constant decline of skills in critical thinking and problem solving among the learners. This claim is also in consonance with the assertion of Magno and Lizada (2015) who disclosed that there must be a constructive alignment between learning competencies and the desired assessment techniques. Based on observations at Halapitan National High School, most of the assessments used in the classroom were pen and paper tests and oral recitations. On the other hand, approaches to teaching and learning in the K-12 curriculum were mostly performance-based. There is a mismatch between the two. Relative to that, the study of Gagarani (2013) found that Mathematics teachers in Bukidnon were more on oral recitations and projects as alternative assessment techniques. Though the attitude of teachers towards using alternative assessment is favorable, their usual practice of giving oral recitations where learners were made to summarize or explain their solutions to the Mathematics problems posed develop only the lower order thinking skills of the students. Critical thinking and problem-solving, the K-12 twin outcomes, were hardly developed. Gaylo and Dales (2017) cited that the said skills were less developed because learners have to go beyond their thinking and make use of their metacognition to do so.

Extent of Exposure of Secondary School Learners to Interactive Games

To determine the extent of exposure of secondary school learners when grouped according to the level of interactivity of games played, mean, standard deviation and frequency were used. The extent of exposure of secondary school learners to the different levels of interactivity in computer games is presented in Table 2. From the tabular presentation, the mean score describes the learners as Slightly Exposed to the various interactive games. Their exposure to these games also described their engagement. It means that the majority of the learners played only during their free time. The results also entail that these learners allotted too little time for online and offline gaming.

Table 2. High School Learners' Extent of Exposure to Interactive Games

Type of Interactive Games	<i>f</i>	%
Highly Interactive Games	33	16%
Moderately Interactive Games	26	12%
Slightly Interactive Games	149	72%
Total	208	100%
\bar{x}	1.87	
SD	0.61	
Qualitative Description	Slightly Exposed	

The frequencies presented details on the preferences of secondary school learners of online and offline games played in terms of its interactivity levels. The results showed that only a lesser number of learners played moderately interactive games while a little higher of these learners preferred playing highly interactive games. It is very evident that the majority of the secondary school learners were exposed to slightly interactive games. In this study, slightly interactive games are those computer games which belong to puzzles, educational, platforms, and strategy games. Games included in these categories include Bookworm Deluxe, Dinner or Cooking Dash, Piano Tiles, Helix Jump, Temple Run, Candy Crush, Wordscape, 4 Pic 1 Word, Chess, and Hill Climb. One feature that is shared by these three categories is the fun factor. These games contain less violent to almost non-violence themes and could be played alone. Out of 208 learners, only 59 preferred playing moderately to highly interactive games such as Mobile Legends, MMPORGs, RPGs or games like DOTA and shooter games such as Counterstrike. This goes to show that in the realm of interactive games like RPGs and First Person Shooter games, the observations in internet cafes only represent a scant part of the gaming population. The results are supported by the survey ran by Pew Internet and American Life Project in 2008 among teenagers in the United States of America. The survey revealed that puzzles, rhythm, adventure, action, racing, sports games were played by 59-74% of the surveyed teenagers while the more serious games such as First Person shooters, role-playing games, survival, and virtual worlds were played by around 10% to 49% of the population. This finding came in as welcome surprise. This ran counter to the notion that these highly interactive games

are the popular choice among secondary school students. Even if the above-mentioned games (RPGs, Shooters, and fighting games) are very popular, it could be noted from Table 2 that only very few learners consistently play these games. In addition, those learners thought to be heavily involved in interactive games are lured by the combination of fantasy, challenge, and curiosity. Their level of engagement could be described as a flow where players do not become mindful of the distractions around him (Kirriemur & Mcfarlane, 2004). Online and offline games draw interests from players for the reason that it offers a wide array of possibilities for exploration of new roles and experiences. In playing Counterstrike, for example, a player could actually play the role of a soldier. The challenge is to conquer the enemies and eventually win each level or stage of the game. Players also develop a sense of curiosity over time as they traverse through each level to complete the game itself. The flow experience of those who frequently play video games could be observed by their seamless concentration in the games they are playing. As observed by the researcher, some players do not complain of getting hunger pangs even after hours of playing video games. Some even ignored physical discomforts during gameplay. Others could actually focus on the game despite the discourteous noise inside internet cafes. Some players use foul words or give out loud laughs during gameplay. This is also explained by Jong et al. (2008) in their review on studies associating video games and learning. The term "flow" is considered as a state of optimal experience, whereby a person is so engaged in an activity that self-consciousness disappears, and time becomes distorted and goal setting is not geared towards gaining external rewards but simply the exhilaration of doing. Due to the flow experience, some learners are hooked with interactive games and are thought to be addicted to those games. One junior high school learner admitted that when he was still in Grade 7, he was hooked into playing DOTA. Most of the time, he played in groups of fours or fives since it can be played online by teams. He stated that it was the belongingness to a team and working with one another in wiping out their enemies that made the game more engaging and appealing. However, his fascination waned as he experienced over fatigue from gameplay. He said that he got bored with the games. Moreover, in an interview with a Grade 11 male learner, he reported that it was his mobile phone that led him not to be so heavily engaged in interactive games. As observed by the researcher, Grade 10 and 11 learners, usually played with their cellphones only during their vacant times or after their classes. Comprehensibly, these students may have limited time to play video games specifically those who were using PCs at internet cafes. Rentals per hour range from ten pesos an hour to twenty pesos. Playing more than an hour may cost much already, and parents do not usually give extra allowance for them to play online games in the internet cafes. This may be a reason why learners spend limited time playing with interactive games. Also, the findings of the study are similar to the results of Choo et al. (2010) in their study among Singaporean teenagers. They had found that only 8.7% of the learners surveyed had obsessive or shall we say addiction symptoms to interactive games. Only a smaller portion of the learners was obsessively hooked in playing interactive games. Learners generally were able to spend time studying and some time for online and offline gaming. The cited study shed light on the gaming habits of Singaporean learners who

consistently made it to the top in the Global Competitiveness Index and perceived as the best in the world in terms of the quality of Science and Mathematics. In Halapitan National High School, learners who self-proclaimed that they were slightly exposed to interactive games divulged that they have a lot of activities and requirements in school that made them have less time in playing with interactive games.

Comparison of the Mathematical Aptitude of Learners when grouped according to the their Extent of Exposure and Interactivity Levels of Games Played

To determine whether there is a significant difference in the mathematical aptitude of secondary school learners when grouped according to their extent of exposure to the different levels of interactivity of computer games played, two-way ANOVA was used at 0.05 level of significance. Table 3 shows a summary of the results. The results revealed that there is no statistically significant difference in the mathematical aptitude of the learners when grouped according to the extent of their exposure to slightly interactive, moderately interactive and highly interactive games. The tabular presentation shows that when the mathematical aptitude of learners was compared with the level of interactivity of the online and offline games played, the F-value had a p-value of which is greater than the significance level of 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected. There is enough evidence to support the claim that there is no significant difference in the mathematical aptitude of secondary school learners who played different interactive games. The different genre of interactive games and their elements of interactivity did not significantly influence the mathematical aptitude of the learners. In terms of the comparison between the learners' mathematical aptitude and extent of exposure to online and offline games, the results revealed no statistically significant difference between the two variables. The F-value of the compared variables generated a p-value which is greater than the level of significance (0.05). The decision is not to reject the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in learner's mathematical aptitude and their extent of exposure to interactive games. There is enough evidence to support the claim that there is no significant difference between the mathematical aptitudes of the learners when grouped according to their extent of exposure. This means that the amount of time played by the students in the different types and genres of interactive games do not matter when we consider their mathematical aptitude. It does not follow that a very exposed gamer will have a poor mathematical aptitude.

Table 3. ANOVA Results on the Test of Difference

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	77133.478 ^a	11	7012.134	1.239	0.263
Intercept	11959419.52	1	11959419.52	2113.095	0.00
Interactivity Level	1272.734	2	636.367	0.112	0.894
Exposure to Interactive Games	8116.190	3	2705.397	0.478	0.698
Interactivity Level *Exposure to Interactive Games	25770.462	6	4295.077	0.759	0.603
Error	1109295.002	196	5659.668		
Total	49913099.45	208			
Corrected Total	1186428.480	207			

As such, learners with average to high mathematical aptitude is comparable to learners with low average to below average mathematical aptitude in terms of playing online and offline games. This implies that whether or not learners play *Minimilitia* or *Bookworm Deluxe*, its influence is not certain to their mathematical aptitude. Likewise, their mathematical aptitude as determined by the NCAE results does not reflect learners' game preference in highly interactive games, moderately interactive games and slightly interactive games. According to an informal interview with a guidance counselor, those who played role-playing games such as *DOTA*, *Grand Theft Auto*, and First Person shooter games such as *Counterstrike* and *Crossfire* were more likely to incur absences and cutting classes. Most of these students are regarded as online and offline game addicts. There was no mention about learners who frequently played other interactive games. Some students who play heavy online and offline games are really noted for their absences, and even cutting class offenses. With their absence, their grades and school performance are affected. Based on observation, not all students who played these types of games missed or skipped classes just to play RPGs and first-person shooter games. During a semi-structured interview with some learners at Halapitan National High, there were more learners in the cream classes who played a variety of games including highly interactive games. It can be understood then that those who flunked or incurred poor performance in school, may lack the commitment, study habits and discipline as what the honor students have in common. The latter were able to manage their time wisely such that their academic activities were not affected by their engagement with interactive games. These findings are parallel to Unsworth et al. (2015) results. They found out that there was a weak to almost zero relations between interactive game experience, preferred genre, and the development of fundamental cognitive abilities. As observed, learners with low academic performance may have experienced poor time management as opposed to other students whose performance were not affected by time allotted for gameplay and the genre of games played. The result is parallel to the findings of Satwicz and Stevens (2008) that online and offline games improve the quantitative reasoning of its players. Even if the intention of the player is just to be entertained by playing interactive games, it could be said that students may have better spatial skills such as visualization and quantitative reasoning which could lead to better mathematical aptitude. However, the mathematical aptitude of students who play interactive games needs to be developed to fully maximize the visuospatial skills that are enhanced by constant exposure to gameplay. Taking into consideration the highly visual games preferred by learners, Mathematics teachers could use manipulatives and visualization activities to engage these learners. Geometry presents a number of opportunities for players who are engaged in interactive games such as analyzing distances between points, approximate lengths, and areas. These skills are needed to play several types of interactive games. Becker (2005) reported that playing puzzles and strategy games rely heavily on logical and mathematical intelligence since it requires the ability to plan and manipulate a fairly complex set of resources. In fact, even simpler games require counting and arithmetic. However, in the current study, the mathematical aptitude of the learners could be considered that it was influenced by the games they preferred playing. In addition, Prensky (2002) expounded that in playing Tetris, a

puzzle game, pattern identification is developed as the player tries to flip and insert pieces or blocks of different shape into forming a straight line. Mathematics is an important component in describing and analyzing motions. Students should learn the process of active inquiry, of the discovery of relationships, of formulating and testing conjectures, and of critical and analytical thinking. In many cases, the process is more important than the content. Searching for patterns might well be the most important experience the student will have in Mathematics. These experiences develop habits and skills of pattern-seeking that can be extremely valuable as the learner encounters new ideas. On the other hand, the findings of the study contradict the results of Ferguson (2010) who found that children who displayed expertise at mildly violent games such as role-playing games were likely to display higher order thinking skills. Role-playing games induced its players to develop characters in the game, both the protagonists and antagonists, customize tools and instruments, the environment, and over-all, design the progression of the game. It is observed that players are aware that playing interactive games such as *DOTA* requires higher-order thinking skills. Players need to plan ahead and decide wisely on what tools and gadgets to use. A player has to plan to win, and at the same time, he is enriching inventory of resources such as health and wealth. In addition to this, the gamer takes on problem-solving tasks to outperform the enemies. Enemies could be Artificial Intelligence in a game based on its design when playing alone or those manipulated by other players. The results in the study of Tobias and Ispa (2008) opposed the findings in the present study. They found out that several learners with high scores in Mathematics played in a low amount of time in interactive games with high spatial content. With interactive games, players have to keep track of the different movements of the characters in the games such as role-playing games (RPGs) and strategy games. Further, players focused also on manipulating objects to complete a pattern or a configuration of pieces of objects to form a figure, especially in puzzle genres. On the other hand, the present study found that learners who played different interactive games demonstrated low average scores in the NCAE mathematical ability subtest despite playing interactive games which are highly spatial. The learners in the present study were also slightly exposed to interactive games that means their engagement can be viewed as a low amount of time. Griffiths (2002) postulated that interactive games have great positive potential together with their entertainment value. He claimed that the success attained by using online and offline games in addressing a specific problem or teach a certain skill should be considered by educators for the improvement in the delivery of education in this digital age. He also mentioned that it is clear from research findings that the negative consequences of playing interactive games could be attributed to the excessive time spent in the gameplay. However, in 2016, Gonzales and fellow researchers found that students who were more engaged with interactive games had higher achievement except for those students who had addictive tendencies. Their findings were corroborated by the findings of Posso (2016). In Australia, Posso examined the results of over 12,000 students in the 2012 OECD's PISA and their online and offline gaming habits. It was found out that those who were engaged with online and offline games exhibited higher scores than students who did not play video games. He further said that it might be that the skills acquired by

playing online games are associated with generalized knowledge and skills required in studying Mathematics, Reading, and Science. It was also revealed in the study that absenteeism and failure in previous grade level contribute to underachievement in the academic endeavors of students. Aside from contradictory results, the findings of the present study validated the results of previous studies. The findings of the study are similar to the findings of Wakil et al. (2017) and Dumrique and Castillo (2018). The academic achievement of learners who played interactive games is somehow not affected by the time they spent playing. Cummings and Vanderwater (2007) claimed playing interactive games may lead to neglect in doing academic works. This means that instead of doing an assignment, studying, and reading, students may be tempted to spend more time playing. Due to the so-called flow experience during gameplay, learners may lose track of time, hence, their schedule for studying was disturbed. These irregularities in their schedule may affect their academic achievement in general. The said claim was strengthened by the findings of Burgess et al. (2012). Accordingly, students engaging with interactive games have a greater tendency to negate from doing homework. As such, playing video games is negatively associated with academic performance. This means that the more a student is engaged with video games, the lower is the academic achievement. However, this is not true in Singapore. In 2010, Choo and fellow researchers found that only around 8.7% of their participants displayed addictive gaming tendencies. Meaning to say, the majority of the students who engaged with interactive games managed to strike a balance between recreation (interactive games) and studying. This implied that Singaporean students, who are among the world's best students in Mathematics and Science, were not affected by their video gaming habits. Chang (2009) reported that students thought of Mathematics as dull and boring but when they play video games, they said they have fun interacting and keeping track with their scores to advance to the next level or win the games. With that, the role of teachers in the classroom is very crucial in making Mathematics more interesting to students. The fact that students who play video games are using numbers and patterns in playing video games, then, it could be said that their computational skills and quantitative reasoning are enhanced. However, it seems difficult to change their views that classroom Mathematics is different from the Mathematics they get to experience while playing.

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